

Deliverable Report D7.2

Project Quality Management & Management Plan

Project & Programme Information	
Project Acronym	INSIGHT
Project Full Name	Integrated Models for the Development and Assessment of High Impact Chemicals and Materials
Grant Agreement No.	101137742
Work Programme	HorizonEurope Cluster 4 - Digital, Industry and Space
Call	RESILIENT VALUE CHAINS 2023 (HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01)
Topic & Title	HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01-22: Integrated approach for impact assessment of safe and sustainable chemicals and materials
Instrument	Horizon Europe – Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Project Start Date	01 January 2024
Duration	48 months

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Associated Partners from (a) Switzerland, (b) United Kingdom, (c) Korea, (d) Brazil, (e) Australia, and (f) USA received national funding from (a) the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI), (b) Innovate UK (UKRI), (c) The National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF), and (d) the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAESPE).

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1.0	28.06.2024	Finalisation & Submission	TAU	EC	Submission

¹ R= Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports); DEM = Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs; DEC = Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.; DATA =Data sets, microdata, etc.; DMP = Data management plan; ETHICS = Deliverables related to ethics issues; SECURITY = Deliverables related to security issues; OTHER = Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

² PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page); SEN = Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement; Classified R-UE/EU-R = EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified C-UE/EU-C = EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified S-UE/EU-S = EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Acronyms Listed in this Document	
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CDM	Communication & Dissemination Manager
DMP	Data Management Plan
EAB	External Advisory Board
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
EM	Ethics & IPR Manager
FHAIVE	Finnish Hub for Development and Validation of Integrated Approaches
GA	Grant Agreement
GRA	Graphenea SA
IM	Innovation Manager
INSIGHT	Integrated Framework for Mechanistic Impact Assessment
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IOP	Impact Outcome Pathway
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PARC	Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals
PBPK	Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic Modelling
PC	Project Coordinator
PFAS	Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances
PM	Project Manager
PMO	Project Management Office
PSC	Project Steering Committee
QA	Quality Assurance
QM	Quality Manager
QSAR	Quantitative Structure–Activity Relationship
R&D	Research & Development
REA	Research Executive Agency
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
TM	Technical Manager
TOC	Table of content
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides all information related to the management of the project and the quality management plan. It includes project governance, roles and responsibilities, means, and processes to execute the day-to-day activities, communication with the consortium and external stakeholders including the European Research Executive Agency (REA), a quality assurance plan, and risk management.

DISCLAIMER: This deliverable is intended to provide a comprehensive overview of our progress and activities. However, it is important to note that this document is not a legally binding contract like the Grant Agreement (GA). In cases of any discrepancies or conflicting information, the provisions outlined in the GA take precedence over those mentioned in this report. Partners are encouraged to refer to the GA for definitive rules and guidelines.

I Description of the Project

I.1 Project Scope and Objectives

The INSIGHT project aims to develop a user-friendly, innovative, and integrated framework for the development of mechanistic impact assessments of chemicals and materials. This framework will support the development of the next generation Safe(r) and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) chemicals and materials that consider their social, economic, health, and environmental impacts. The project outcomes support stakeholders, regulators, and policymakers in making informed decisions and constitute a comprehensive approach to assessing safety and sustainability.

INSIGHT will drive innovation towards a digital, circular, climate-neutral, and sustainable economy by integrating and democratising cutting-edge AI methods. It will address the current fragmented approaches (i.e., the disconnection, inaccessibility, and inability to use novel computational approaches), via a holistic, integrated, comprehensive, and multi-layered knowledge graph framework. This framework will connect data and models, while adhering to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles that ensure broad accessibility and reusability.

A core component of the INSIGHT project is the development of an integrated computational platform based on the concept of Impact Outcome Pathways (IOP). This platform will integrate the computational approaches developed and used within INSIGHT to provide a mechanistic and integrated evaluation of the social, economic, health, and environmental impacts of chemicals and materials. To achieve this, processes such as Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) following the Product Environmental Footprint methodology, hazard and risk models, social Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), and Life Cycle Costing principles will be used. This holistic approach aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of impacts, develop novel social and economic impact indicators, and facilitate informed decision-making.

The INSIGHT framework will be benchmarked and validated by case studies involving antimicrobial coatings, advanced materials for energy storage, construction applications, and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). These studies will demonstrate the framework's practical applicability and effectiveness in addressing the social, economic, health, and environmental impacts of chemicals and materials. These will provide valuable insights and feedback for further framework refinement.

Collaboration with related frameworks and projects is also essential for ensuring regulatory relevance and broad applicability of the SSbD framework. The project will maintain continuous collaboration with PARC and CompSafeNano, for example, to harmonise methods, data, and metadata reporting, and harmonise their efforts, thus providing a unified and effective framework. This will enhance the overall impact and utility of the INSIGHT SSbD framework and support the development of a dynamic, sustainable economy that respects human health and the environment.

For INSIGHT to achieve its goals, stakeholder engagement is vital for developing an open, accessible, and interactive SSbD framework. The project will collaborate with regulatory-science expert groups and stakeholders to create user-friendly guidelines and decision maps, facilitating the adoption of the SSbD framework by industry and regulators through validated documentation and interactive interfaces. The project will provide open, accessible, and interactive guidelines by using conceptual decision maps to guide users through the decision-making process, helping stakeholders interpret outputs and make SSbD-compatible decisions.

The INSIGHT consortium unites 20 partners (Table I) with expertise in chemical safety assessment, LCA, socio-economic studies, regulatory toxicology, environmental and innovation studies, science and technology, data science, AI, and software development. These partners are from well-known universities, research institutions, and private sector organizations, providing the necessary administrative and infrastructure support for the project.

Table 1 INSIGHT Partners

N°	Role	Short name	Legal name	Country
1	COO	TAU	TAMPEREEN KORKEAKOULUSAATIO SR	FI
2	BEN	NovaM	NOVAMECHANICS LIMITED	CY
2.1	AE	NovaMGR	NOVAMECHANICS MONOPROSOPI IKE	EL
3	BEN	NTUA	ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION	EL
4	BEN	ULEI	UNIVERSITEIT LEIDEN	NL
5	BEN	LIST	LUXEMBOURG INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	LU
6	BEN	MUI	MEDIZINISCHE UNIVERSITAT INNSBRUCK	AT
7	BEN	WH	WARRANT HUB SPA	IT
8	BEN	UPO	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DEL PIEMONTE ORIENTALE AMEDEO AVOGADRO	IT
9	BEN	AUTH	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	EL
10	BEN	AIST	ACUMENIST	BE
11	BEN	GRA	GRAPHENEA SA	ES
12	BEN	7P9-SI	SEVEN PAST NINE D.O.O.	SI
13	BEN	EVO	EVONIK OPERATIONS GMBH	DE
14	BEN	SOLVAY	SOLVAY SA	BE
15	AP	EMPA	EIDGENOSSISCHE MATERIALPRUFUNGS- UND FORSCHUNGSANSTALT	CH
16	AP	UNC	THE UNIVERSITY OF NORTH CAROLINA AT CHAPEL HILL	US
17	AP	HU	INDUSTRY-UNIVERSITY COOPERATION FOUNDATION OF HANYANG UNIVERSITY	KR
18	AP	CNPEM	CENTRO NACIONAL DE PESQUISA EM ENERGIA E MATERIAS ASSOCIACAO PRIVADA	BR
19	AP	LTU	LA TROBE UNIVERSITY	AU
20	AP	UoB	THE UNIVERSITY OF BIRMINGHAM	UK

The coordinator, Professor Dario Greco, is a prominent bioinformatics expert and director of the Finnish Hub for Development and Validation of Integrated Approaches (FHAIVE). The partners have extensive experience in interdisciplinary research. The project promotes inclusion and gender diversity and supports open science in data and publications.

INSIGHT is co-designed by all partners, ensuring their expertise shapes the project's tasks and objectives. Each work package uses multiple disciplines to support interdisciplinary knowledge production. Open dialogue during the planning phase has ensured that all of the partner expertise is used to define the tasks and objectives. Project resources are allocated to each partner to cover necessary costs and responsibilities.

NovaMGR, operating under NovaM, contributes specialised expertise in computational modelling, developing and refining models like LCA, Quantitative Structure–Activity Relationships (QSAR), and Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic Modelling (PBPK). It is a leader in database development, ensuring data integrity and adherence to FAIR principles. NovaMGR identifies and fills data gaps

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through systematic literature reviews and develops the Graphical User Interface (GUI) for the INSIGHT framework, ensuring it is user-friendly and meets regulatory requirements

I.2 Project Work Plan and Breakdown

The INSIGHT project is comprised of seven work packages (WPs, Table 2), each led by a designated beneficiary and covering specific aspects of the project over a defined timeline. WP1, "Specifications Setting & Case Studies", led by UoB, runs from month 1 to month 42 and uses 107 person months. WP2, "Model Graph & Models Implementation," is led by TAU, runs from month 3 to month 42, and employs 148 person-months. NovaM leads WP3, "Data Graph & Data Management," from month 1 to month 48, employing 100 person-months. ULEI oversees WP4, "Mechanistic & Integrated Impact Assessment," from month 1 to month 45, contributing 124.5 person-months. WP5, "INSIGHT SSbD Framework & Stakeholders Acceptance," led by MUI, operates from month 1 to month 48 and involves 110.5 person-months. WP6, "Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication," is led by WH and spans the entire project duration and uses 66 person-months. Finally, WP7, "Project Coordination & Management," led by TAU, also spans the entire project duration and employs 38 person-months.

Table 2 INSIGHT WPs

WP	WP Title	Lead Beneficiary	PMs	Start	End
WP1	Specifications Setting & Case Studies	UoB	107	M1	M42
WP2	Model Graph & Models Implementation	TAU	148	M3	M42
WP3	Data Graph & Data Management	NovaM	100	M1	M48
WP4	Mechanistic & Integrated Impact Assessment	ULEI	124.5	M1	M45
WP5	INSIGHT SSbD Framework & Stakeholders Acceptance	MUI	110.5	M1	M48
WP6	Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication	WH	66	M1	M48
WP7	Project Coordination & Management	TAU	38	M1	M48

The project also uses comprehensive case studies (Table 3) to evaluate specific use cases. The use cases are: assessment of antimicrobial coatings for their safety, sustainability, and regulatory compliance; the evaluation of advanced materials used in energy storage solutions for their health, environmental, and societal impacts; and the examination of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) materials, focusing on their environmental persistence and health impacts.

Table 3 INSIGHT case studies

Use Case Title	Use Case
Antimicrobial Coatings	Assessment of antimicrobial coatings for their safety, sustainability, and regulatory compliance.
Advanced Materials for Energy Storage	Evaluation of advanced materials used in energy storage solutions for their impact on health, environment, and society.
Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS)	Examination of PFAS materials, focusing on their environmental persistence and health impacts.

Project delivery is ensured through the division of each WP into clearly defined tasks (Figure 1), designed to facilitate collaboration and optimise objective delivery. Timely project delivery is also assured through a comprehensive series of milestones (Table 4) and deliverables (Table 5).

2 Project Management and Governance

Table 4 INSIGHT Milestones.

Milestone No	Milestone Title	WP	Partner	Due
MS 1	Reconfirmation of the case studies & their regulatory and knowledge landscapes	WP 1	UoB	M3
MS 2	Identification of publicly available models to integrate	WP 2	AUTH	M3
MS 3	First version of the DMP	WP 3	NovaM	M6
MS 4	Initial drafts of computational pipelines for the case studies	WP 4	ULEI	M8
MS 5	INSIGHT proposal is accepted within the work plan of a relevant OECD expert group	WP 5	MUI	M36
MS 6	Corporate Identity established & dissemination channels set	WP 6	AIST	M4
MS 7	Case Study 1	WP 1	UPO	M30
MS 8	Case Study 2	WP 1	UPO	M42

Table 5 INSIGHT Deliverables

WP	WP Title	Lead Beneficiary	PMs	Start	End
WP1	Specifications Setting & Case Studies	UoB	107	M1	M42
WP2	Model Graph & Models Implementation	TAU	148	M3	M42
WP3	Data Graph & Data Management	NovaM	100	M1	M48
WP4	Mechanistic & Integrated Impact Assessment	ULEI	124.5	M1	M45
WP5	INSIGHT SSbD Framework & Stakeholders Acceptance	MUI	110.5	M1	M48
WP6	Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication	WH	66	M1	M48
WP7	Project Coordination & Management	TAU	38	M1	M48

2.1 Project Management Strategy

Project management monitors all core activities to ensure the successful progress, delivery, and completion of the project on time and on budget as set out in the Description of Work and Grant Agreement (GA). WP7, led by TAU, manages and coordinates the project by tracking the scope, timely delivery, costs, resources, and quality of project outcomes. Any changes needed to achieve goals are always discussed with the partners, and decisions taken are based on partners agreement and are taken in consultation with the Project Officer and the European Commission (EC). Good communication practices are crucial for ensuring that information reaches the appropriate partners, so that timely, efficient decisions can be taken. Quality management contributes to project quality control and quality assurance activities that facilitate efficient collaboration between the consortium partners and delivery of project outcomes. Risk management processes and techniques provide the means for foreseeing, identifying, evaluating, and controlling of the potential project risks, focusing on their precautionary diagnosis and handling.

2.2 Project Management Structure

INSIGHT management consists of the Executive Board, the Project Management Office, the General Assembly, the Advisory Board, and the Project Steering Committee (Figure 2).

The Executive Board (EB) is comprised of the Project Coordinator (PC) Prof Dario Greco. The Project Management Office (PMO) consists of: the Project Manager (PM) Ms Hanna Hästbacka, the Quality Manager (QM): Lisa Bregoli (WH), the Technical Manager (TM): Angela Serra (TAU), the Innovation Manager (IM): Isella Vicini (WH), the Communication & Dissemination Manager (CDM): Steffi Friedrichs (AIST), and the Ethics & Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Manager (EM): Tommaso Serchi, Lisa Bregoli, Peter Wick and Dario Greco and the Work Package Leaders: WP1: Prof. Iseult Lynch (UoB), WP2: Dr. Angela Serra (TAU), WP3: Dr. Antreas Afantitis (NovaM), WP4: Prof. Willie Peijnenburg (ULEI), WP5: Dr. Martin Paparella (MUI), WP6: Dr. Bregoli (WH), WP7: Prof Dario Greco (TAU).

The **PC** is the intermediary between the partners and the EC and will perform all tasks assigned to him as described in the **GA** and the Consortium Agreement (**CA**). The **PM** is responsible for timely and efficient project implementation, ensures proper allocation of resources, facilitates communication between the project partners, and organises project-related events and meetings. The **PM** is also responsible for monitoring potential risks and their mitigation. The **QM** is responsible for all quality assurance processes. The **TM** supports the **PC** in making technical decisions and supervises and provides guidance on the technical progress of the projects. The **TM** provides timely foresight, suggestions, and solutions to any technical risk that could impact project objectives and timing.

The **IM** is responsible for: –

- i) monitoring the on going project work, identifying the innovation and exploitation potential of the technologies developed;
- ii) recommending IPR Results protection and projecting an adequate IPR Results protection plan;
- iii) identifying and documenting the intellectual property ownership conditions of the intermediate and final project results;
- iv) outlining and keeping updated the exploitation plan for the individual technologies and for INSIGHT as a whole;
- v) monitoring the publication activities of the partners and preventing any premature disclosure of confidential information that might affect patentability and/or the Results' IPR protection;
- vi) directing the exploitation and Results IPR protection within the project.

The **CDM** is responsible for the design, preparation, and implementation of the project Dissemination and Communication Plan, which aims to create awareness in relevant scientific communities. The **CDM**

coordinates all dissemination activities and sharing of ideas with external stakeholders and ensures the widest possible exposure of project outcomes to its target groups.

The **EM** makes sure that activities such as the engagement of citizens and local stakeholders and use of social media data are conducted in an ethical manner, by taking into account sex and gender considerations and respecting the GDPR regulations. WP Leaders, are responsible for: –

- i) planning and implementing the scientific and technical work of the WP, in coordination with all relevant partners;
- ii) ensuring that the time schedule is maintained and identifying any discrepancies to the PC;
- iii) initiating corrective actions for project deviations (if required);
- iv) consolidating partner information and preparing the reports for submission to the PC;
- v) ensuring that objectives, deliverables, and milestones of the whole WP and the detailed activities within the WP are delivered on time.

The **EB** functions as the supervisory body for the effective execution of the project. It monitors and manages the day-to-day operations and is accountable to the General Assembly (**GA**ss).

The **GA**ss is the ultimate decision-making body that makes decisions on high-level management and strategic issues. It comprises representatives from each beneficiary, namely the **PC**: Prof Darui Greco (TAU), the Deputy Coordinator (DC): Dr Andreas Afantitis (NovaM) and the Principal Investigators (PIs) from each consortium partner. Each PI is responsible for designating a substitute when not able to join the GAs.Representatives. The PIs are Dario Greco (TAU), A. Afantitis (NovaM), H. Sarimveis (NTUA), Willie Peijnenburg (ULEI), Tommaso Serchi (LIST), Martin Paparella (MUI), Isella Vicini (WH), Francesco Dondero (UPO), Denis Sarigiannis (AUTH), Steffi Friedrichs (AIST), Beatriz Alonso (GRA), Joh Dokler (7P9-SI), Gottlieb Georg Lindner (EVO), Jacques-Aurélien Sergent (SOLVAY), Peter Wick (EMPA), Alex Tropsha (UNC)m Tae Hyun Yoon (HU), Diego S. T. Martinez (SNPEM), Dave Winkler (LTU), Iseult Lynch (UoB)

The **External Advisory Board (EAB)** consists of leading domain experts who provide important insight and operational support to the project activities: –

- Dr. Nanna Fyhrquist (Karolinska Institutet, Sweden), an expert in immunotoxicology, epidemiology, and One Health;
- Dr. Roberto Nitsch (AstraZeneca, UK), the director of drug safety;
- Dr. Vania Vilas-Boas (University of Porto, Portugal), an expert in nanotoxicology;
- Dr. Andreas Kremer (ITTM, Luxembourg), an expert in data management, sharing, FAIRness, and privacy;
- Prof. Kunal Roy (Jadavpur University, India), an expert in computational modeling in chemical safety;
- Dr. Dan Villeneuve (EPA, USA), an expert in AOP development and integration in regulatory assessment;
- Dr. Emma Palo (NextChem, Italy), an expert in industrial processes in chemicals and materials development and production; and

Other members will be added to the AB as the project progresses.

The Project Steering Committee (**PSC**) consists of the PC, TM, IM and the EAB, which is responsible for monitoring the impact of the project, following its Key Performance Indicators, and providing strategic guidance.

Figure 2 Organisation Structure of INSIGHT

3 Management Processes and Tools

3.1 Deliverable Preparation

According to the GA, INSIGHT has 35 deliverables, each assigned to one responsible partner. The partner in charge of the deliverable is responsible for collating the necessary information from the relevant partners, its development and harmonisation, and its timely and of high-quality submission to the PC. Each deliverable is reviewed internally by 2 senior partners not involved in its development. After the quality review, and making required amendments (if needed), the final version of the deliverable is uploaded by the PC to the EC portal. The deliverable preparation process is depicted in Table 6.

Table 6 Deliverable preparation time plan.

Task	Deadline
First draft for internal review ready	30 days before deadline
Lead partner sends deliverable draft to PC	30 days before deadline
PC identifies and sends draft to internal reviewers	30 days before deadline
Reviewers complete and submit their reviews	16 days before deadline
Final draft with internal reviews ready	15 days before deadline
Reviewed deliverable saved to Google Drive for everyone's comments	15 days before deadline

Review by the Quality Manager and provision of feedback to the deliverable leader	10 days before deadline
Approval of the draft by the PC and preparation of finalised version	5 days before deadline
Coordinator submits the final deliverables to the EC	By the deliverable deadline

Any deviations from the time plan should be communicated by the deliverable leader to the PC as soon as possible. The time plan can be adjusted if previously agreed between the author, the reviewers, the PC, and the Project Officer. The deliverables marked as “public” will be uploaded to the INSIGHT website while the deliverables marked as “sensitive”, will be only made available to the EC and the consortium partners via the project’s repository and the EC portal.

3.2 Document formats and naming conventions.

To harmonise the development of resources and to ease the communication process and the identification of documents and versions all partners are advised to use specific tools and respective formats (Table 7) and naming conventions based on the principle of self-explanatory titles and versions. The general file name conventions are as follows:

INSIGHT_[name of the document]_Vxy_date_[partner acronym/person name].FileExtension

- The name of the document shall be as concise as possible but also self-explanatory i.e., Kick_Off_Project_Meeting_Minutes
- The date should be presented in the form ddmmyyyy i.e., 12032021.
- The partner acronym or person name should be used as defined in the GA i.e., TAU for the TAMPEREEN KORKEAKOULUSAATIO SR.

Table 7 Tools and formats recommended to be used in INSIGHT

Type	Format	Production Tool	Version
Documents	.docx	Microsoft Word	“Word 2010 or later”, Google Docs
Scientific Papers	.tex	Latex	Any desktop or online release
Data in tabular form and graphics	.xlsx	Microsoft Excel	“Excel 2010 or later”, Google Docs
Presentations	.pptx	Microsoft PowerPoint	“PowerPoint 2010 or later”, Google Docs
Images	.jpeg, .png etc	Any software tools that can produce images	various
Portable Document Format	.pdf	Any software that can produce .pdf files	various
Compressed Files	.7z	Any software that can produce .7z (7-Zip) files	various

3.3 Reporting to the EC

INSIGHT has 3 reporting periods aligned with progress payment requests (Table 8). The Periodic reports are compiled with contributions from all partners. WP Leaders are responsible for the gathering, collation, and harmonisation of each participating partner’s input for their WP and respective tasks. The PC has the overall responsibility and coordination for developing, harmonising, and delivering the periodic report. The finalised periodic reports are to be submitted to the portal by the PC, within

60 days after the end of the reporting period. Additionally, there will be 3 Interim Progress Reports documenting the 6 months progress in between the reporting periods of the project without being related to payment requests. These are included in WP7 and namely as deliverables:

- D7.4 Short Interim Management Report: M12
- D7.5 Short Interim Management Report: M24
- D7.6 Short Interim Management Report: M36

Similarly, for these reports, the PC is responsible for the coordination and the submission of the reports. All partners will be asked to contribute based on templates and instructions that will be circulated by the PC.

Table 8 Reporting Periods

RP No	Month from	Month to	Reporting Type	Deadline Reporting
1	1	18	Periodic report	60 days after end of reporting period
2	19	36	Periodic report	60 days after end of reporting period
3	37	48	Periodic report	60 days after end of reporting period

3.4 Conflict Resolutions

Project and quality management activities, and communication to all partners about their commitments and responsibilities, will ensure the proper implementation of the project plan and the achievement of its objectives. Decisions will normally be taken by the responsible partners based on the work to be conducted, as described in the GA. Transparency and good communication among the project members are key to avoid challenges and conflicts before they arise.

Partners may need to resolve various issues and reach agreement during the project. This will start with informal contacts e.g., oral discussions or ad-hoc meetings, and may escalate to include written notification in terms of email, minutes etc.

The PC is responsible for the overall conflict resolution. The general principle is to resolve conflicts at the earliest time (Figure 3), starting from the task level with strong emphasis on the use of negotiation skills. Task leaders and Work Package leaders should notify the PC as soon as possible when conflicts arise so that intermediate resolution can be achieved. Conflicts that are not being solved on the PC level will be communicated to the General Assembly. Any corrective measures will be via the GA and the CA. Good communication among all parties is key for resolving any conflicts.

Figure 3 Escalation levels regarding conflict resolution communication and resolving

Disputes, which cannot be solved amicably, shall be finally settled by the courts of Brussels. (INSIGHT Consortium Agreement, Based on DESCA – Model Consortium Agreement for Horizon Europe)

4 Communication Processes and Tools

4.1 Internal Communication and Monitoring

The communication processes and tools below form the communication framework of INSIGHT. These will serve as a guide for internal communication throughout the project and can be adjusted as required. The CDM in collaboration with the PC will take a central and proactive role in ensuring effective project communication and facilitating the seamless implementation of the INSIGHT work plan.

4.2 Project Team Directory/Repository

Google Drive will be used as the central repository for the project. All partners will be able not only to share documents but also include written texts, minutes of meetings etc.

4.3 Emails and Mailing lists

Direct email will be used as a common means for sharing information and addressing day-to-day businesses of the project. An INSIGHT mailing list has been created (insight@lists.tuni.fi)

Where needed, specialised mailing lists will be created and employed, e.g., per WP.

4.4 Online Meetings Platform

Regular online calls between partners will be held. Partners are free to choose the most appropriate platform i.e. Google Meet, Skype, Webex, Zoom etc. The online meetings organised by the PC will be held over Zoom.

4.5 Organisation of Meetings

For the organisation of meetings, the online service Doodle will be used to define the date and time of the meeting.

4.6 Project Meetings

Table 9 summarises the number and types of meetings, their schedule, the organisers, participants, location, and related documents.

Table 9 INSIGHT meetings

Meeting	Time	Organizer	Participants	Location	Deliverables
Kick-off meeting	M1 (15-16/02/2024)	PC	All project partners	Face-to-Face/virtual event	Agenda, Meeting presentations, Minutes - Action Plan
Plenary Meetings Project	Every 12 months (M12, M24, M36, M48)	PC	All project partners	Face-to-Face/virtual event	Agenda, Meeting presentations, Minutes - Action Plan
Weekly Meetings Project	Every week	PC	All project partners	Online meeting	Agenda, Minutes - Action Plan
Ad hoc meeting	Whenever needed	All project partners based on topic and need	Project partners based on topic needs	Face-to-Face/virtual event	Agenda, Minutes - Action Plan
General Assembly Meeting	At least once per year	PC and Members of the GA	Face-to-Face/online meeting	Minutes - Action Plan	

4.7 External Communication

For external communications, the consortium will establish a website and communicate with external stakeholders via e-mail, social media accounts, and social platforms (e.g., X formerly known as Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn).

All partners will produce high-quality presentations and scientific papers for publication in specialised national and international conferences and peer-reviewed journals, as well as simplified press releases suitable for lay audiences, demonstrating the impact of the project for a wide range of readers.

In all external communication tools (including the web) and materials (e.g., leaflets, posters) a reference to the project and the European funding will be made, with the project acronym (INSIGHT) and the GA number (No 101137742). These efforts will be maintained throughout the project to raise awareness and ensure high visibility of the project results.

More information about the external communication will be presented in the Deliverable “D6.3 Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (PDEC) first release” to be submitted in M6. To optimize the communication activities, each partner assigns a communication manager responsible for monitoring and implementing the communication plan.

4.8 Communication with REA

The PC is the responsible contact point for the project, for the communication with REA or the EC. The PC is responsible for ensuring that the project portal is always kept up to date e.g., communications, milestones reached, public deliverables, peer-reviewed publications, and progress reports submitted. Moreover, the PC is responsible for providing any information requested by the REA as well as for informing the partners about information that should be shared from the EC. The partners should not communicate with the EC directly, except in special cases or at the EC’s request

that has been previously discussed and agreed upon with the PC. In all other cases, the PC will communicate any issues to the EC.

5 Quality Assurance Plan

5.1 Quality Assurance Overview

According to the Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK)³ Guide as published by the Project Management Institute, “Quality Assurance is the process of auditing the quality requirements and the results from quality control measurements to ensure that appropriate quality standards and operational definitions are used”.

Quality assurance is a fundamental part of the implementation of the project and will be performed throughout the duration of the project by all the partners. The quality assurance plan is based on the plan-do-check-act cycle introduced by W. Edwards Deming⁴ (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Quality assurance principles

- Plan: relates to the objectives, processes, tools, and resources needed to deliver the results according to the work plan and the project requirements
- Do: refers to the implementation of the planned work
- Check: refers to monitoring and evaluating the project outcomes and services based on the planned work and the requirements
- Act: refers to the actions taken, if necessary, to make corrections and improve outcomes and performance.

³ [PMBOK Guide | Project Management Institute \(pmi.org\)](https://www.pmi.org)

⁴ [PDSA Cycle - The W. Edwards Deming Institute](https://www.wedeming.com)

5.2 Roles and Responsibilities

TAU, as the coordinator of the project, will ensure that the project partners are aware of the Quality Assurance Plan and how each partner contributes to the successful implementation of the project and achievement of the project's quality requirements. Moreover, TAU is responsible for the control of documented project information, including storage and backup and version control of changes. Google Drive, chosen as the central repository for the project, supports both requirements and as such ensures that this information can be available at any time.

Each WP leader is responsible for monitoring and controlling the implementation phase of their tasks and sub-tasks and ensuring conformity with the quality requirements. Technical testing and user validation will be utilised throughout the implementation of the project measuring the satisfaction of INSIGHT's quality requirements.

5.3 Quality Criteria

All products of INSIGHT either on the technical level (i.e., services, models etc.) or in written form such as reports, deliverables, and publications must be of high quality. Quality criteria are based on the principles of completeness, correctness, and punctuality⁵. Regarding the content, completeness is seen as covering in depth the topic without missing any important aspect or making redundancies. The accuracy is seen in the context of clear statement of the results, sufficient evidence support for the research outcomes, and minimisation of errors and ambiguities. All materials must follow the visual identity of the project and use the INSIGHT templates as well as conform to the specifications of the EC. Punctuality, refers to the timely delivery of based on predefined deadlines.

5.4 Deliverable Quality Assurance Processes

A total of 35 deliverables will be submitted by the end of the project. The deliverables will follow the same template set up by TAU, who will provide guidelines about their use, timeline, and expected results to all partners (see section 3.1). Internal review of each deliverable will focus on scientific merit, consistency and clarity of the document, relevance and coverage of the topic, and language. For each deliverable 2 partners will be assigned as reviewers.

The final quality control of the deliverable will be conducted by the Quality Manager of the project. For the ease of communication and consistency, all deliverables will follow the naming conventions defined in section 3.2:

INSIGHT_[Deliverable Number]_Title_of_the_Deliverable_vX.Z_[Responsible Partner], where "v" refers to the version, Z is used for the different versions during the preparation phase and X for the major releases of the documents. The draft and final versions of the deliverables are edited only by the Deliverable leader, the partners who are responsible for it, and the PC.

Example of a working document/draft version:

INSIGHT_D7.2_Project_Quality_Management_And_Management_Plan_v0.1_NovaM

Example of a final document

INSIGHT_D7.2_Project_Quality_Management_And_Management_Plan_v1.0_NovaM

The template for the deliverables prepared by TAU, includes all essential information of the project and the content of the deliverable including call identifier, GA number, title, acronym, duration, document revision history, assigned roles and description, table of content, list of figures and tables (if applicable), list of acronyms, executive summary.

⁵ Bots, J.M., Heck, E. van, Swede, V.van, "Management information", pub. CAP Gemini Publishing BV, Rijswijk, 1990, pp. 550-555

5.5 Milestones and Quality Controls

To ensure the quality of the project, eight Milestones have been established. The Milestones are also quality control points where the progress of the project is evaluated (Table 10). Each Milestone will be reviewed by the QM and the PC before submitting to the EC. The QM will be responsible for communicating any required amendments to the responsible Milestone partner.

Table 10 INSIGHT milestones and Quality Control Measures

Milestone No	Milestone Name	WP No	Lead	Quality Control	Due (month)
1	Reconfirmation of the case studies & their regulatory and knowledge landscapes	WP1	20-UoB	INSIGHT industrial partners confirm specific chemicals/materials to focus on and their industrial/regulatory relevance	3
2	Identification of publicly available models to integrate	WP2	9-AUTH	List of available models, their location, implementation and FAIRness status	3
3	First version of the DMP	WP3	2-NovaM	Verify that the DMP includes provisions for long-term data curation, preservation and archiving	6
4	Initial drafts of computational pipelines for the case studies	WP4	4-ULEI	Fully documented computational pipelines specific for the three case studies	8
5	INSIGHT proposal is accepted within the work plan of a relevant OECD expert group	WP5	6-MUI	Work plan of the OECD expert group contains the INSIGHT proposal	36
6	Corporate Identity established & dissemination channels set	WP6	10-AIST	A logo for the INSIGHT project and website is created. Social media channels are set up.	4
7	Case Study 1	WP1	8-UPO	Case Study activities 1	30
8	Case Study 2	WP1	8-UPO	Case Study activities 2	42

6 Risk Assessment

6.1 Risk Management Introduction

Risk management refers to all activities undertaken for identifying, analysing, monitoring, and controlling potential risks that could affect the planning, implementation, execution, and delivery of the project. Risk management is a continuous process that will be undertaken throughout the lifetime of the project.

Risks will be minimised and managed by using well-established methodologies for project planning and project control. The splitting of project work into work packages minimises internal risks as well. The PM and TM are responsible for monitoring the various processes and identifying potential risks. The PC, PM, and the TM in cooperation with the EB will be mainly responsible for handling risks, identifying solutions and allocating resources (where applicable), and for informing all partners when necessary.

6.2 Risk Management Plan

Risks will be identified and analysed throughout the project based on the risk life-cycle processes consisting of risk identification, risk analysis, risk evaluation, risk mitigation and risk tracking (Figure 5). Each partner is responsible to communicate to the PC any potential risks.

Figure 5 Risk Management Processes

Each identified risk will be evaluated based on the Risk Assessment Matrix (also found as Probability and Severity risk matrix) against its impact and likelihood. The Risk Assessment Matrix is an easily comprehensible way of visualising the potential risks (Figure 6). Depending on the severity of each risk, different preventive and/or mitigation measures will be taken. The level of likelihood will be defined based on Table 11.

Figure 6 Risk Assessment Matrix (source: [https://www.maintworld.com/Partner Articles/Using-a-Risk-Assessment-Matrix-to-Improve-Maintenance](https://www.maintworld.com/Partner%20Articles/Using-a-Risk-Assessment-Matrix-to-Improve-Maintenance))

Table 11 Guidelines for using the Risk Assessment Matrix

Level	Likelihood	Probability	Impact
I	Not Likely	~10%	Negligible

2	Low Likelihood	~30%	Minor
3	Likely	~50%	Moderate
4	Highly Likely	~70%	Significant
5	Near Certain	~90%	Severe

The definition of the risk level is calculated based on the relation between Probability/Likelihood and Impact with the “Impact value” weighting more than the “Likelihood value”. The risk levels are explained in Table 12.

Table 12 Definition of risk levels

Risk Level	Definition
LOW	Has little potential to cause disruption of schedule, increase in cost, or disruption of performance. Normal effort will probably be able to overcome difficulties.
MODERATE	Can potentially cause some disruption of schedule, increase in cost, or disruption of performance. However, special effort will probably be able to overcome difficulties.
HIGH	Likely to cause significant serious disruption of schedule, increase in cost, or degradation of performance even with special effort and close monitoring of the contracting activity.

6.3 Identified Risks

As defined in Annex I of the GA, several risks and risk-prevention/mitigation measures have been already defined at the submission of the proposal (Table 13).

Table 13 INSIGHT risks and risk-mitigation measures

Risk No	Description	WP	Proposed Mitigation Measures
1	The current AOP framework might not be flexible enough to accommodate other types of impacts, posing challenges to the development of the IOP framework. (L/M)	4	INSIGHT partners have already solid experience working with the concept of modulating factors, which are external factors that can affect the relationship between a stressor (such as a chemical) and an adverse outcome. In the context of the AOP framework, modulating factors can be used to represent economic and social factors that can affect the relationship between a chemical stressor and an adverse outcome
2	Major changes in regulatory regimes emerge during the project, requiring a change in focus (L/L)	1-7	The consortium and its structure are sufficiently lean and agile to adapt to regulatory changes; engagement with regulators, ensures foresight & allows adaptation of approaches in real time.
3	Failure to engage all relevant stakeholders (L/M)	5,6	Risk is mitigated by including multiple representatives of some of the main stakeholders in the consortium and having a strong link to the regulatory bodies such as OECD.
4	Some necessary datasets are not Open Access / FAIR (H/M)	3	Access will be negotiated with the data owners; datasets used will be FAIRified on behalf of the data owners if necessary
5	Suggested impact paths are too complex and/or data initially identified to execute case studies will not be	1	The case studies have been carefully designed based on multiple data sources already available to the INSIGHT partners. In any case, the industrial partners of INSIGHT have a collective commercial portfolio of several thousands of chemicals/materials, allowing to

	available or not appropriate, making the execution of the analysis difficult or impossible. (L/H)		easily define similar case studies based on other data sources, if needed. Moreover, the INSIGHT computational framework is designed to work with a broad applicability domain, allowing to model many chemicals/materials of different types. The models in the INSIGHT framework will also be able to accommodate situations in which less input data is available, resulting in a higher degree of uncertainty.
6	Model graph (WP2) and data graph (WP3) development may pose technical challenges with respect to algorithms used. (M/M)	2,3	The choice of specific algorithms is partially driven by the nature of data and hence cannot be entirely decided a priori. However, the INSIGHT partners have already solved most uncertainties in their previous work. They are also familiar with unexpected scenarios and master a wide range of methods and tools that can be easily assembled to produce optimal analytical pipelines.
7	Data modelling in INSIGHT relies on advanced AI algorithms, whose ability to effectively learn data patterns depends on the underlying training data. Not enough data is available or data available is not of sufficient quality (L/H)	2,3,4	Preliminary analysis suggests that publicly available data can easily contribute with over 70 million data points. This is sufficient for the analysis and level of granularity we aim at. INSIGHT partners will actively look for additional data sources to be integrated into the Data graph and hence used to train the AI-based models. The INSIGHT computational infrastructure is scalable and able to work in a tiered and round-robin manner. It is therefore capable of accommodating new data points at any step.
8	Different chemicals/materials impact indicators can result in discordant impact assessments, which can create confusion and uncertainty for decision-makers. (H/M)	4,5	INSIGHT project has the advantage of partnering with experts in multi-decision criteria making, which is useful for addressing discordant impact assessments of chemicals/ materials. The decision maps and INSIGHT framework GUI will always return output that can be interpreted by the end users.
9	For the success of INSIGHT, predictive models of impact assessment should become part of industrial R&D pipelines. For this, higher levels of standardisation need to be achieved, with the risk of challenging implementation and adoption of the computational solutions. (M/M).	4,5	The INSIGHT consortium includes partners who can work at high level of standardisation (GLP, ISO, etc.). Moreover, INSIGHT partners have numerous, on-going collaborations with industrial and regulatory entities that will ultimately allow to explore the implementation outcomes in an operational environment.
10	Partner needs to leave the consortium (Lack of contribution, Bankruptcy, other problems) (L/H)	1-7	If a partner repeatedly fails to fulfil their obligations, the project coordinator will give a warning and ask them to take corrective measures by a particular deadline. If the partner still does not comply after multiple requests, they will be asked to exit the project, and the consortium will follow the same contingency plan as it would for a partner drop out. Remaining activities and funds will be offered to existing partners; new partners will be sought, if necessary.
11	OECD Expert Group members may not receive sufficient support from their national authorities to include the INSIGHT concepts and	1,4,6	INSIGHT project partners (TAU, MUI, LIST) are permanent members within several relevant OECD expert groups and will seek bilateral exchange with key players in these groups before submitting any proposal. In case the INSIGHT proposals cannot be included in the OECD Expert Group work, we will identify key

	tools suggested by the INSIGHT partners into their work programme. (M/M)		players for discussion of the concepts within workshops outside of OECD, which will be less demanding in terms of timely resources.
12	Change of key employees in research institutes or participating companies can complicate the project implementation.(M/M)	2,3,5,7	There are several experienced researchers in the research institutes which enables the rearrangement of duties with decent efforts. In addition, substitutes for the company contact persons will be named.
13	Conflict amongst the partners. (L/M)	1-7	Conflict resolution measures will be clearly assigned and agreed upon in the CA. If a partner leaves the project, the consortium will search for another partner able to replace it.

7 Effort and Cost Management

7.1 Effort and Cost Management Overview

The total effort and budget of the projects are defined in the GA and particularly in Annex I and Annex 2 respectively. Effort and cost management aims to ensure that the project is conducted within the predefined Person-Months and budget. The PC in collaboration with all partners will monitor the effort and resources by comparing the actual numbers to the data defined in the GA. Beneficiaries with general accounts established in a currency other than the euro must convert the costs recorded in their accounts into euro, at the average of the daily exchange rates published in the C series of the Official Journal of the European Union (ECB website), calculated over the corresponding reporting period, as stated in paragraph 21.3 of the GA. Any cost/effort change will follow a thorough communication between the affected partner and the PC. Approvals for extreme project effort/cost changes may require a contract amendment with the EC.

Effort and Cost Monitoring and Reporting

The financial part of the periodic report includes the financial statements (individual and consolidated; for all beneficiaries/affiliated entities), the explanation on the use of resources (or detailed cost reporting table, if required), the certificates on the financial statements (CFS) (if required; see Article 24.2 and Data Sheet, Point 4.3 of the GA). The financial statements must detail the eligible costs and contributions for each budget category and, for the final payment, also the revenues for the action (see Articles 6 and 22 of the GA).

Conclusions

This deliverable presents all relevant information regarding project management and quality management plan based on current best practices and what is defined in the DoW and accepted by all partners by signing the Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement. The document shall be used as a reference for all processes and means that will be used by the project.

